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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes a summary of existing and planned research infrastructures in the central Arctic Ocean, as presented and discussed at the HiAOOS-organized Research Infrastructures workshop held in Tromsø, Norway, 24-26 January 2024. Concepts and requirements for a pan-Arctic multipurpose mooring network for ice-ocean observations, tomography, and geo-positioning were discussed along with possibilities for future collaboration. Enhanced collaboration with the Argo float communities was recommended. Collaboration has been established with the Polar Connect community, working with plans for a trans-Arctic communication cable that can also be used for research.

The workshop was organized in sessions with the following themes: 1) fixed research installations, 2) moving platforms and 3) technologies, methods, tools, and data delivery chains. This report follows the same structure, followed by a brief section with emerging new collaborations and suggestions for additional assets (moorings, buoys, and floats) that will fill identified gaps in the Arctic Ocean Observation System.

In total 31 registered and participated in the Workshop. The participants came from Europe, North America, and Asia.

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1 Introduction

For this open workshop we invited research infrastructures (RIs) and research and innovation projects working with ocean observing systems, ocean observing technologies, methods, and tools. The purpose was to inform each other about ongoing in situ observing activities in the central Arctic Ocean. Focus was on new observing capabilities and capacity for the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.

The workshop was organized in three sessions:

Session 1. Fixed installations including mooring networks and sea floor installations.

Session 2. Moving platforms including gliders, floats, ice buoys and airborne platforms.

Session 3. Technologies, methods, tools, and data delivery chains

The workshop was tailored to contribute to sustain and enhance collaboration and coordination in Arctic Ocean Observing following up recommendations from EU-INTAROS (2016-2022) and EU Arctic Passion (2021-2025).

1.1 Context of the workshop

The workshop was planned and organized by the EU-funded HiAOOS project (hiaaos.eu) and the UD-AOOS: “Technologies and collaboration for sustained Arctic Ocean Observation System” project funded by the Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

UD-AOOS is focused on planning and collaboration for strengthening the Norwegian role in the establishment of an Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS). The project will engage with national and international organisations and with commercial technology providers to collaborate in planning, coordination, and implementation of an Arctic Ocean Observation System.

In the years to come HiAOOS and UD-AOOS will organize several workshops together, as well with other projects, RIs, and organizations. This first workshop and the workshops to come are also a support to the development of the Arctic GOOS Regional Alliance.

1.2 Organization of the report

This report follows the same structure as the workshop with three thematic sessions, followed by a section with the outcome of the workshop. It includes proposed and emerging new collaborations, and suggestions for technologies to fill the pronounced gap in under-ice observations e.g. mooring networks for ice-ocean observations, acoustic tomography, and autonomous under-ice navigation in the central Arctic Ocean.

2 Session 1: Fixed location infrastructures

2.1 The HiAOOS and HIAATS multipurpose mooring infrastructure

Presented by: HiAOOS coordinator Hanne Sagen, NERSC, and HiAATS coordinator Matthew Dzieciuch, SIO

The HiAOOS (High Arctic Ocean Observation System, see <https://hiaaos.eu/>) and HiAATS (High Arctic Acoustic Thermometry Soundscape) projects build on a number of earlier, successful experiments with acoustic sound sources and receivers. The multipurpose mooring system facilitates the collection of ice-ocean observations, including ocean sound, and provides acoustic signals for acoustic tomography and localization of floats and navigation of gliders (Mikhalevsky et al. 2015, Worcester et al. 2020). Multipurpose mooring networks have been deployed and proven both regionally (Fram Strait 2008-2016), Beaufort Sea (2016-2017) and across the Arctic Ocean (TAP 1994, ACOUS (1999), and CAATEX (2019-202)). In the regional networks 200-300 Hz sweeps were used, while in the Trans Arctic experiments 20 Hz and 35 Hz M-sequences have been used.

In 2024, HiAOOS funded by EU and the HiAATS funded by US-ONR will join forces and deploy a basin-wide network of three multipurpose moorings with low frequency sound sources (35 Hz – M) and acoustic receiver arrays. A fourth mooring with a receiver array is planned to increase the coverage of tomography. Each mooring includes a suite of other sensors covering basic oceanographic parameters (hydrography, currents, sea ice, etc). The moorings are positioned to cover most of the Nansen and Amundsen Basins in the Arctic Ocean (Figure 1). The system will provide acoustic signals for thermometry (along the green lines), and for geo-positioning of floats. For more information see Section:

Figure 1. Map of planned HiAOOS/HiAATS moorings (red dots) in the Nansen and Amundsen basins of the Arctic Ocean.

The moorings will include low frequency passive acoustic recorders for detecting earthquakes, and broad band passive acoustic recorders record sound from marine mammals and ship traffic. The four-mooring system will be deployed from 2024-2026. In this period, HiAOOS will provide ocean observations, acoustic thermometry, and test geo-location of floats under the ice using 35 Hz M-sequence signals.

In 2025 the low frequency acoustic system in the interior Arctic will be supplemented with 2 moorings North of Svalbard, which includes instrumentation for acoustics (900 Hz) and ice-ocean observations. Stinger and NAXYS TECH will deploy a mooring to test new technology for data access and recharging of batteries without recovery of moorings using ROVs. These moorings will be deployed within the red triangle in coordination with the mooring systems described in Section 2.3.

Recently, a infrastructure proposal – NOR-HiAOOS was submitted to the Research Council of Norway aiming to expand and sustain the HiAOOS network of moorings, and buoys over the next decade.

2.2 The Norwegian Polar Institute’s monitoring program in the Arctic Ocean

Presented by: Arild Sundfjord, NPI.

The Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) has monitored outflow of sea ice and water masses from the Arctic Ocean in western Fram Strait since the early 1990s, inflow of Atlantic Water to the Arctic Ocean north of Svalbard since 2012, and environmental conditions in the western Nansen and Amundsen Basin since 2022. The observing program in the central Arctic Ocean comprises multi-disciplinary moorings, high-resolution transect cruises, and deployment of drifting sea ice buoys. The moorings carry sensors for hydrography, sea ice drift and draft, basic biogeochemistry, as well as automatic water samplers and sediment traps. Together with bi-annual cruises that augment the moored sensor measurements with additional parameters, particularly a larger suite of biogeochemical samples and biological observations from nets and trawling, this provides a comprehensive view of the state and seasonality of these under-studied ocean basins. The geographical coverage is enhanced by annual deployments of drifting sea ice buoys. NPI’s monitoring is closely aligned with the development of the Atlantic-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory network (see Sec 2.6).

Figure 2. Norwegian Polar Institute’s standard transect line (red dotted line), mooring locations (small yellow dots) and sea ice buoy drift paths (coloured lines) from 2022.

2.3 IOPAN moorings in HiAOOS and A-TWAIN

Presented by: Agnieszka B. Møller, Institute of Oceanology, Polish Academy of Science (IOPAN)

IOPAN has operated moorings in the Atlantic Water (AW) inflow region along the continental slope north of Svalbard since 2012. This has been part of several international projects such as A-TWAIN (<https://www.npolar.no/en/projects/a-twain/>) and INTAROS (<http://www.intaros.eu/>), as well as with support from IOPAN’s internal projects. The AW inflow monitoring has been a collaborative effort with a number of international partners.

From 2025, IOPAN and AWI will deploy a new mooring over the upper part of the continental slope north of Svalbard to test modern technology for upper-ocean profiling and satellite transfer of collected ocean data and acoustic transfer of data from moored instruments in the water column.

Figure 3. Concept sketch of winched profiling of top float with integrated satellite transmission (from Normen Lochthofen, AWI).

2.4 AWI's plans for Central Arctic Ocean research infrastructure deployments from 2024

Presented by: Benjamin Rabe, AWI

AWI will continue their long-term observations in the central Arctic Ocean. In 2024, the ArcWatch-II expedition will carry out an extensive hydrographic survey, including physics, biochemistry, geochemical sampling (GEOTRACES program) as well as biological sampling (including fishing). Multi-disciplinary moorings deployed in 2022 will be serviced, and new drifting sea ice buoys will be deployed.

Figure 4. Planned cruise track for AWI's 2024 ArcWatch-II expedition.

2.5 Science & Technology Development in the Office of Naval Research Arctic Program

Presented by: Craig Lee (UW) and Lee Freitag (WHOI)

For the last decade, several ONR-funded programs have investigated ocean and sea ice dynamics and processes in the Canadian Basin of the Arctic Ocean. Development and application of multi-scale autonomous observing capabilities have been an integral part of this project portfolio. For year-round operation of autonomous underwater platforms in ice-covered areas, development of acoustic navigation and communication capabilities have been central, and over the last couple of years, multi-platform full-year operation has been successfully demonstrated (Arctic Mobile Observing System (AMOS) project), utilizing long-endurance SGX gliders, profiling floats and ice-based platforms supported by 900 Hz (fixed and mobile) and 35 Hz (long-range, baseline) sound sources for underwater geolocation and 10 kHz acoustic modems for two-way communication and data transfer. Activities are planned to continue in 2024 and beyond.

Figure 5. 2024 plans for fixed-location long-range (VLF, 35 Hz; red and cyan) and medium-range sources (AMOS, 900 Hz; black).

2.6 Developing the pan-Arctic network of Distributed Biological Observatories

Presented by: Anna Nikolopoulos, NPI

Since 2010, the Distributed Biological Observatory (DBO, see <https://dbo.cbl.umces.edu/>) has functioned as a “detection array” for ecosystem changes and trends in the Pacific sector of the Arctic Ocean. Similar marine observational networks are now being established in the Davis Strait region (DS-DBO), the Atlantic-Arctic sector (A-DBO, see <https://arcticpassion.eu/adbo/>) and in the Siberian Sector (S-DBO).

The DBO concept aims to leverage existing monitoring programs in the Arctic Ocean and expand their measurements to include inter-comparable ecosystem-level observations. It builds on active, long-term involvement of scientists working across disciplines in dedicated geographical areas toward better integrated and available observations, strengthening the regional assessments of the coupled marine system.

This coordination of efforts is based on joint open planning of the observations carried out by different projects and nations. The gain of such a regional work plan is an increase of the observation frequency, and of the number of sampled parameters, at identified key sites, as well as better use of infrastructure. The DBO sites are typically biological hot spots, centred on locations of high productivity, high biodiversity and high rates of biological change. They capture both contrasting and complementing environments within each region and cover key ocean phenomena and processes under rapid change. Moreover, the key sites should suit long-term funded efforts, including long-term mooring programs, as well as project-based efforts and more opportunistic “passers-by” sampling.

The establishment process for the new regional networks, and the development of the pan-Arctic entity, is to a large degree shaped through open DBO Community meetings held twice a year; with a regional scope in fall, and pan-Arctic at ASSW in spring.

A major part of these collaborative efforts is currently facilitated by the EU Horizon project Arctic PASSION. The four DBOs place regional observations in a broader pan-Arctic context and will be an important tool for monitoring system-wide physical and ecological changes. Hence, the pan-Arctic DBO cluster is a highly relevant contribution to the marine part of the pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS; <https://arcticpassion.eu/intro>)

Figure 6 (left). The pan-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory networks

2.7 KOPRI cruise and mooring plans in the Eastern Arctic 2024

Presented by: Arild Sundfjord on behalf of Eun-Jin Yang and Joo-Hong Kim, KOPRI

KOPRI has conducted a comprehensive study of ocean process and sea ice dynamics in the Northern Bering Strait, Chukchi sea and East Siberian sea since 2012. As part of KOPRI's long-term observing efforts in the Pacific region of the Arctic Ocean (K-AWARE program), a cruise with RV Araon will be carried out in summer 2024. This will comprise service of the multidisciplinary KAMS moorings (see Figure 7), extensive water column sampling, and sea ice station work. These KOPRI activities are an important part of the Siberian Sector DBO (see below).

Figure 7. Repeat transects (in yellow) and mooring locations (in Green) that will be visited during KOPRI's 2024 RV Araon cruise.

2.8 The NABOS cruise and mooring program

Presented by: Igor Polyakov, IARC

The NABOS observing program (see <https://uaf-iarc.org/nabos/>) has covered evolution of ocean heat, freshwater, stratification, and effects on the regional sea ice cover in the eastern Nansen and Amundsen Basins since 2004. The last sampling and moorings service cruise took place in autumn 2023, and the next one is planned for 2025. NABOS is an important part of the evolving S-DBO network (see above) and aims to expand the measurement program to include more biological parameters through collaboration with additional partners.

Figure 8. NABOS cruise and moorings plans, along with KOPRI's adjoining mooring location which illustrates the close connection between the programs.

3 Session 2: Moving platforms

3.1 Technologies and Opportunities for Sustained, Autonomous Arctic Observing

Presented by: Craig Lee (UW) and Lee Freitag (WHOI)

Utilizing the long (35 Hz) and medium (900 Hz) range acoustic sound source system (see Section 2.3) augmented with ice-tethered two-way communication “gateway” buoys, gliders have been operating autonomously under sea ice in the central Beaufort Sea for year-long missions as part of the ONR-funded AMOS project. Gliders were deployed directly through holes in the sea ice and commanded to find and rendezvous with drifting gateway buoys that were up to 100 km away. Gliders approached, rendezvoused with, and followed their gateway buoys, uploading data and receiving new commands. This was done fully autonomously, without any human interaction or intervention.

Using the same 900 Hz and 35 Hz sources for geolocation, Argo floats equipped with acoustic navigation receivers were also successfully tested in the same area in 2023. The floats were deployed hanging from a line suspended beneath the drifting sea ice and then released on command to begin their profiling missions. The cost of both acoustic navigation receivers and acoustic two-way micro-modems has come down significantly and the aim is, through open-source protocols, to facilitate larger-scale production of equipment that can be used on Argo floats, and more generally, on any other autonomous under-water platform to be used in ice-covered waters.

Figure 9. Illustration of AMOS navigation, communication and platform network as deployed in 2023.

3.2 A low-CO2 smart autonomous multiplatform system to monitor the Arctic Ocean

Presented by: Virginie, Ramasco, Akvaplan-niva

Akvaplan-niva contributes to new applications and development of autonomous technology and sensors to increase knowledge of northern marine ecosystems. Gliders and uncrewed surface vessels are used in combination for remote autonomous monitoring and in-situ validation of model predictions. The autonomous technology is typically deployed with the support of third-party vessels of opportunity, allowing extensive sampling with a low carbon footprint. The platforms are equipped with standard oceanographic sensors and in addition carry equipment focusing on biological sampling, such as e.g. echosounders, hydrophones, optical and biogeochemical sensors, eDNA samplers, etc. depending on the specific application. Data are ingested into the Kongsberg Discovery’s Blue Insight system for contextualization, real-time analysis and intuitive visualization for both researchers and stakeholders.

Figure 10. Concept sketch of field campaign in JPI Oceans Clin-BluFeed project.

3.3 Sea ice buoys at AWI: Recent activities and plans for 2024/2025

Presented by: Andreas Preußer, AWI

The long history of AWI sea ice buoy deployments in the central Arctic and Transpolar led to an archive of several hundred individual instruments of various types (sea ice mass balance buoys, snow buoys, surface velocity profilers, CTD buoys and many other types; also including contributions from partner institutions) on the AWI sea ice portal (<https://data.seaiceportal.de/>) as well as on the data publisher portal Pangaea (www.pangaea.de). The total number of buoys in the archive was greatly increased in 2023 by a targeted deployment of more than 70 individual buoys, primarily using the German research vessel Polarstern (PS138/ArcWatch-1), but also by opportunistic use of the French tourist icebreaker Le Commandant Charcot. An example image from PS138 (station “ICE5”) of a larger buoy array with annotated instrument types is shown in the figure below. A new uniform processing scheme has been developed within the EU-funded Arctic PASSION project to derive snow, ice, and ocean interfaces for past and recently deployed thermistor buoys (SAMS/SIMBA type). This will add value to the existing archived raw data.

Future planned AWI sea ice buoy deployments in the Arctic so far mainly comprise the two Polarstern cruises PS144 (ArcWatch-2) in August-September 2024 and CONTRASTS in July-September 2025. They will be complemented by the use of other deployment platforms (e.g., Tara Polar Station in 2025/2026).

Figure 11. Drone image of several buoy installations on sea ice floe “ICE5” during the ArcWatch-1 (PS138) expedition in 2023. Featured are: MetOcean Snow Buoy 2023S127; SAMS SIMBA 2023T106; Pacific Gyre CTD Buoy 2023O20; WHOI ITP (2023W6); Bruncin Radiation Station 2023R25; Pacific Gyre SideKick Buoy 2023K1; Cryosphere Innovations SIMB 2023I11; Dartmouth College SnowTATOS and Ablation stakes.

3.4 Euro-Argo in the Arctic, Nor-ARGO in the Arctic, IOPAN floats in the Arctic under ArgoPoland

Presented by: Claire Gourcuff, Euro-Argo, Kjall Arne Mork, IMR, Agnieszka Beszczynska-Möller, IOPAN

The international Argo programme has so far deployed more than 4000 autonomous profiling floats, some of which with biogeochemistry sensors (BGC-Argo). The Euro-Argo programme (see <https://www.euro-argo.eu/>) sustains and optimises the European contribution to the international Argo programme, providing, deploying and operating 25% of the international network. Among the Euro-Argo members, NorArgo2 (<https://norargo.no/>) has been the Norwegian contribution, with focus on the Nordic Seas, and hence also some floats that have drifted into the central Arctic Ocean. Similarly, the ArgoPoland program (<https://www.iopan.gda.pl/hydrodynamics/po/Argo/argo.html>) has deployed floats in the Nordic Seas annually since 2009.

The new OneArgo design features algorithms for safe operation under sea ice. Although some methods exist to estimate profile position under-ice, this remains an issue for Argo. As of January 2024, 94 active floats were profiling in the Arctic region, but very few of these inside the central Arctic Ocean proper. To enhance high Arctic Argo coverage, an international Argo Polar mission team has been established. Some of the goals of this group are to share knowledge and expertise of technological advances and issues for Polar Argo, mission programming, ice avoidance algorithm tuning and under ice positioning capability (e.g. navigation, acoustic geolocation and post-processing techniques). A new proposal is in preparation (Horizon Europe call) for Euro-Argo, with the participation of most of its members, including a task on the Argo design in the Arctic.

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Figure 12. Concept sketch of ice-avoidance algorithm for Argo floats.

3.5 ARCTic Airborne Observing System (ARCAOS)

Presented by: Tom Rune Lauknes, NORCE

Aircraft can be very efficient at filling gaps in the “observational pyramid” between satellite-based observations and in situ measurements. A Dornier Do-228 passenger/cargo aircraft operated by Lufttransport AS, and permanently stationed in Longyearbyen, Svalbard, has been modified to carry scientific instruments, and scientific observations can be collected both during regular operations and tailored flights. The current science payload includes a hyperspectral imager, a medium-format camera, and a broadband radio that can be used to download data from remote installations (such as drifting sea ice platforms). Other planned sensors as part of ARCAOS are a SWIR imaging spectrometer and an imaging synthetic aperture radar (L-band and X-band), as well as atmospheric in-situ sampling capable of observing aerosol size distribution, trace gas (O₃, CO, CH₄, H₂O), and meteorological parameters such as temperature, pressure, humidity, wind.

4 Session 3: Technologies, methods and tools

4.1 Acoustic technology for acoustic thermometry and geo-positioning

Presented by: Matthew Dzieciuch, Scripps Institution of Oceanography

This presentation reviewed the technology and results from the 2019-2020 Coordinated Arctic Acoustic Thermometry Experiment (CAATEX). The purpose of the experiment was to measure the travel-time of low-frequency sound across the Arctic in order to infer the heat content. Before the experiment there was a large uncertainty in the expected transmission loss due to sound scattering from the rough ice. We have a much better idea of the losses now and this will inform the design of future Arctic acoustic experiments. Since the signals used for thermometry can also be used for navigation, it seems obvious that any new source installations should be dual use. Using our acquired knowledge of acoustic propagation one of our first steps will be to develop an energy budget for the tomography and navigation transmissions. A navigational error map should also be developed to explore various source location scenarios.

4.2 Arctic Acoustics Communication and Navigation

Presented by: Lee Freitag, WHOI

This presentation went through previous work on development of acoustic communication and navigation, that has led to the set up presently used in the Beaufort Sea: low-frequency (LF, 900 Hz) for navigation and communication, very low-frequency (VLF, 35 Hz) for longer-range navigation, combined with 10 kHz gateways for data offload. This source-and receiver infrastructure allows for multi-use of the technology; both for ocean acoustics research and under-ice navigation of gliders and floats. There is broad agreement that all Arctic VLF sources should provide navigation services, and navigation sources should contribute to understanding of ocean acoustics. However, tomography requires precise navigation and timing, which is presently not available on ‘low-cost’ VLF systems. There is thus a need to work on “dual-use” VLF sources.

Next Steps for the WHOI acoustics group and collaborators include 1) Continue float receiver integration and testing, 2) Look for international opportunities to collaborate, 3) Commercialization of under-ice capability (under development) 4) Development to reduce receiver power consumption and increase capability (longer signals).

Other topics to be explored further for the community include 1) signal parameters, 2) locations and quantity of sources, and 3) funding and deployment support that will provide for sustained acoustic navigation for floats and gliders over the next decade for Arctic Argo and other programs.

4.3 Acoustic propagation and underwater geo-positioning of moving platforms

Presented by: Lora Van Uffelen, University of Rhode Island

When underwater acoustic signals arrive at receivers hundreds of kilometres away, they arrive over a span of several seconds due to the fact that sound speed is not constant with depth. Underwater acoustic propagation models can be used to predict the pattern of these arrivals, and the method of Acoustic Arrival Matching (AAM) can be used to align peaks in measured acoustic data with arrival predictions to refine estimates of range between the source and receiver (Van Uffelen et al., 2013). In this way, the acoustic propagation physics can be used to improve ranging and therefore geo-positioning for autonomous platforms in the ocean. This has been demonstrated both using manual and automated methods for acoustic data collected on Seagliders in

the Philippine Sea and manually for data collected on Seagliders in the Beaufort Sea for acoustic source transmissions centred around 250 Hz (Van Uffelen et al., 2016; Graupe et al., 2019; Graupe et al., 2022). In the Beaufort, a sound-speed minimum around 180 m depth allows transmission to long ranges but results in a complicated arrival structure. This acoustic arrival structure is highly dependent on the sound-speed profile, highlighting the importance of measured oceanographic profiles for accurate acoustic predictions. The signals being planned for HiAOOS/HiAATS will be at a lower frequency (~35 Hz) and acoustic predictions show a more distinct acoustic arrival structure which should lead to more straightforward acoustic ranging for geolocation.

4.4 Localization of floats using the HiAOOS multipurpose acoustic network

Presented by: Espen Storheim, NERSC

Drifting floats rely on surfacing to obtain a GPS fix and transmit data. In the Arctic Ocean, the sea-ice cover prevents this, and the floats may drift for a long time without a fix, while still collecting data. The proposed geometry of the moorings in the HiAOOS multipurpose acoustic network is well suited for tracking floats in the Eastern Arctic, particularly in the Transpolar drift. Work is being carried out on how to use the tomographic signals for localization, and how to optimize the receptions, e.g., which depths are best suited. Acoustic and oceanographic data from previous experiments, together with data from other sources, such as from the Ice Tethered Profilers (ITP), shipborne observations, and the International Arctic Buoy Program (IABP), is currently being used to get a better understanding of the conditions in the area, and to develop and improve methods and tools for localization.

A localization algorithm has been implemented based on ranges between sources and a receiver (Fig. 15a), and studies on how the source placements affect the performance of the localization have been started. An example of the latter is shown for the proposed HiAOOS mooring geometry in Fig. 15 (b), and the benefit of adding a source in the Western Arctic is indicated in Fig. 15(c). Lighter colours represent good performance. Although this is a simplified analysis, it still provides a useful indication of the performance, especially for the localization of drifting floats.

Figure 15: Example of localization of a drifting float using the HiAOOS multipurpose acoustic network (a). The range from each source to the float is calculated from the measured travel time and shown as range circles, where the intersection of these circles is the location of the float. The Horizontal Dilution of Precision (HDOP) is shown for the proposed HiAOOS source geometry (b), and by adding a sound source in the Western Arctic (c).

4.5 Earthquake monitoring in the Arctic combining seismological and passive acoustic data

Presented by: Mathilde Sørensen, University of Bergen

Seismic activity in the Arctic Ocean region is mainly concentrated along the slowly spreading Gakkel Ridge. Due to its remote offshore location and the relatively small magnitudes of most event, this activity is difficult to monitor with land-based stations. During the EU funded INTAROS project (2016-2021), three Ocean Bottom Seismograph (OBS) systems were deployed along the spreading ridge west of Svalbard. Analysis of the data shows that even this limited offshore network allows for a threefold increase in the number of detected events during the deployment period as well as significant improvements in location accuracy of the detected events (Jeddi et al., 2021). The OBS systems were each equipped with three seismograph components and a hydrophone sensor (Figure 1). Recordings show that the hydrophone provided high-quality recordings of the events that may be used for earthquake detection and location.

A major challenge related to OBS deployments is that it is challenging to obtain long, continuous time series of data which are needed to fully understand the seismic activity in an area. Furthermore, it is logistically very demanding to deploy and recover OBS systems in ice-covered regions and the risk of losing instruments is high. To overcome these challenges, we plan during the HiAOOS project to equip the four HiAOOS moorings with each a continuously recording low-frequency hydrophone for earthquake monitoring. The data will be analyzed together with data from the land-based seismic networks to improve detection and location of earthquakes along the Gakkel Ridge.

Figure 16: Recordings of a $M_w 4.5$ earthquake on 21. June 2019 on the three OBS systems (OBIN1, OBIN2 and OBIN3). For each instrument, the three seismograph components and the hydrophone component (HDH) are shown.

4.6 Workflow for ocean and sea ice data in HiAOOS

Presented by: Agnieszka Beszczynska-Möller, IOPAN

This presentation showed the plans for development of methods for improved data processing and production of advanced data products and visualizations in the HiAOOS project. The initial steps in this work have been to; 1) identify and collate different data sets, 2) provide tools to calculate derived quantities from measured parameters, and 3) provide tools for advanced QC across different data sets. Development of tools consists of the following steps:

- methods/tools for interpolation (temporal/spatial)
- methods/tools for averaging over different time scales, selection of subsets or categorization
- tools to obtain full statistics of key variables
- tools for visualization of time series (point and full profiles, derived variables)

This part of HiAOOS (WP3) also concerns application of data products in other tasks, such as providing tools for comparison/validation against other data sets (e.g. reanalyses, climatologies, gridded fields from in situ and satellite observations).

Figure 17. Schematic illustration of production chain for HiAOOS data products

4.7 Polar Connect - Connectivity and sensors across the Arctic Ocean.

Presented by: Magnus Friberg, Swedish Research Council/SUNET

Polar Connect (<https://nordu.net/polar-connect/>) is supported by several Northern European states and the European Commission. Its aim is to establish a high-speed fibre optic connection between Europe and East Asia across the Arctic. The project is initiated by the Nordic National Research and Education Networks (NRENs). The NRENs are actively exploring options and rationale for equipping a future Polar Connect cable with sensing capabilities, such as Direct Acoustic Sensing and SMART sensors, both to protect the cables integrity and to allow for using the cable as an instrument for environmental monitoring and research in the central Arctic Ocean.

Figure 18: Map showing the proposed routes for the two complementary fiber optic connections across the Arctic, Polar Connect (Green) and Far North Fiber (Yellow). Polar Connect is driven by the Nordic Research and Education Networks (NRENs) with support by EU through the Connecting Europe Facility program. The strong interest from the NRENs is due to an identified need for resilient communication between Europe and East Asia for research collaborations and the potential to use the fiber optic cable as a long-term instrument for monitoring and research in the Arctic Ocean.

Polar Connect is an open consortium and we seek collaboration with partners interested in fiber optic connectivity between Europe and Asia as well as partners interested in using a future fiber optic cable for Arctic research and monitoring. More information is available in the Polar Connect Vision 2030, please see https://northern-eu-gateways.nordu.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/D5.3_Vision-2030-whitepaper.pdf

4.8 Management of a multi-asset, integrated ocean observing system: data and infrastructure

Presented by: Benoît Pirenne, Ocean Networks Canada

Ocean Networks Canada (ONC, see <https://www.oceannetworks.ca/>) operates infrastructure that monitors the west and east coasts of Canada and the polar regions to continuously deliver data in real-time for scientific research, societal benefits and technological innovation.

ONC's infrastructure supports ocean research within and across disciplines ranging from geophysics, oceanography, marine acoustics, marine ecology, geochemistry to microbiology facilitated by the co-location, at every observatory site, of sensors serving multiple fields of research. The observatories supply continuous power and Internet connectivity to a broad suite of scientific instruments located in coastal and deep-ocean environments. ONC's digital networks host thousands of sensors distributed in, on and above the seabed along

with mobile and land-based assets (e.g., ferries, autonomous floats, moorings, and coastal radars) that provide essential data.

Figure 19. Schematic illustration of Ocean Networks Canada means to collect and acquire ocean data.

ONC's powerful online data management system Oceans 3.0 is the most visible aspect of ONC and the primary means by which ONC's diverse user communities can access, analyze, visualize, and present observatory data. ONC has placed particular attention to the FAIR principles of research data management to ensure not only Findability and Accessibility (through the multiple Oceans 3.0 data access methods), but also Interoperability (through the provision of data in many different formats) and Reusability (by ensuring that ample metadata is describing everything from instrument provenance and calibration, locations and configuration parameters, data quality assessment values using QARTOD, etc.). Over 18 years of data have now accumulated in the archive for some locations and decadal, high time resolution datasets can be analyzed to address climate questions. In the Arctic, ONC has been operating a cabled observatory in Cambridge Bay, NU continuously since 2012 and has citizen science programs ongoing throughout the North, off the coast of communities in Nunavut and Labrador. ONC is wholeheartedly supporting Arctic cable projects such as Far North Cable and Polar Connect as they have the ability to support passive sensors along their path through the SMART concept, use Distributed Acoustic Sensing, or support branches and spurs that could power nodes and platform with instrumentations.

Figure 20. Locations of observatories around Canada, as part of Ocean Networks Canada.

4.9 Ice information and satellite imaging to support vessel operations in the high Arctic.

Presented by: Nick Hughes, MET

The Norwegian Meteorological Institute’s (MET) sea ice service can provide customized support for field campaigns and offshore operations, including 1) Satellite images, 2) Ice charting, 3) Sea ice forecasts, and 4) Meteorological forecasting. MET also runs the Ice Watch shipboard sea ice observing programme (<https://icewatch.met.no/>). Examples of comprehensive field campaign support efforts include the CG Svalbard CAATEX mooring recovery cruise from Svalbard to the Beaufort Sea.

4.10 Digital platforms and data delivery chains for marine in-situ observations

Presented by: Torill Hamre, NERSC

The HiAOOS project uses and enhances digital platforms for ingesting, processing, analysing, and visualising in situ observations from moorings, buoys and vessels collecting ocean and ice data from the Arctic Ocean. The functionality of these platforms are extended with methods and tools for calculating new parameters and generating higher level data products. NERSC implements workflows for data publishing using Airflow, an open-source platform widely used for data engineering and science. Generated data products are published through the Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC). Data products from NMDC and other open data infrastructures is then ingested into a digital twin Blue Insight, developed by Kongsberg Discovery.

Figure 21. HiAOOS Data Delivery Chain (Hamre et al., 2023)

4.11 Data policies and licenses

Presented by: Stein Tronstad, NPI

This presentation described principles and recommendations for data management. The recommendations derive primarily from data policies from [Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research](#) (2022), [Southern Ocean Observing System](#) (2022), [IOC/IODE](#) (2023), and, more specifically for the Arctic region; Arctic: IASC and the Arctic Council.

The recommended core principles are as follows:

- Data must be ethically open
- Data should be free
- Data must be provided in a timely manner
- FAIR principles should be applied to the greatest extent practicable
- All data must be accompanied by a complete set of metadata
- Data should have persistent and globally unique identifiers
- Data must be labelled as reusable
- Data should be attributable and attributed
- Data must be appropriately preserved for the long term
- Data management and long-term curation must be planned and resourced

5 Cross-project and cross-platform collaboration possibilities

Here follow some examples of topics that were further explored during discussions at the workshop:

Icebreaker operations in the central Arctic:

Several cruises with ice breakers are planned in 2024 and in the years to come. In late summer/fall 2024 the rough schedule is,

- Kronprins Haakon operates in the deep Arctic in July/August, (NPI)
- KV Svalbard HiAOOS cruise in Nansen and Amundsen Basin in August/September (NERSC)
- Polarstern will operate in the Nansen and Amundsen Basin in August/September (AWI)
- Oden will operate North of Greenland/Gakkel Ridge in August/September (Stockholm University)
- Kronprins Håkon will meet with Oden near Gakkel ridge in August/September (NORCE)
- The Korean ice breaker RV Araon in the summer of 2024 (KOPRI)
- Crossing Arctic Ocean in 2024 will be USCGC Healy (August-October) and the French expedition ship Le Commandant Charcot (September).

It is important to investigate possibilities for co-ordination/collaboration between cruises planned for the Eurasian Basin in 2024 and beyond. Topics for collaborations may include tandem operations, sampling plans, sea ice buoy deployments, mooring operations etc.

Dedicated meetings will be organised in March and April 2024 to start the discussions. One suggestion to follow up is to discuss if we from 2025 can plan annual cruise planning meetings as part of the Arctic Science Summit Week, which take place typically in March/April every year.

Pan Arctic mooring network:

Moorings provide year-round under-ice observations and can in principle observe the whole water column with a cluster of multidisciplinary sensors. The drawback is that the moorings are expensive, and they need to be recovered to download of data and refurbishment of all components before they are redeployed for typically two years. There are several mooring systems in the Arctic Ocean some of these are listed in section 2.1-2.8. Most of these mooring systems are situated at the rim of the Arctic Ocean.

Multidisciplinary moorings: Most of the systems placed in the Arctic Ocean are equipped with instruments for ice ocean observations but some also with biogeochemical sensors. From Section 2.6: “Since 2010, the Distributed Biological Observatory (DBO) has functioned as a “detection array” for ecosystem changes and trends in the Pacific sector of the Arctic Ocean. Similar marine observational networks are now being established in the Davis Strait region (DS-DBO), the Atlantic-Arctic sector (A-DBO) and in the Siberian Sector (S-DBO). The DBO concept aims to leverage existing monitoring programs in the Arctic Ocean and expand their measurements to include inter-comparable ecosystem-level observations.”

Acoustic navigation mooring networks. The University of Washington and the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution have over a couple of decades developed technology and acoustic networks for navigation of gliders in different regions of the Arctic e.g., Davis Strait and Beaufort Sea. They are now “utilizing the long (35 Hz) and medium (900 Hz) range acoustic sound source system (see Section 2.3) augmented with ice-tethered two-way communication “gateway” buoys, gliders have been operating autonomously under sea ice in the central Beaufort Sea for year-long missions as part of the ONR-funded AMOS project.”

Multipurpose mooring network. The concept of multipurpose mooring network has been explored and developed since 2008 in Fram Strait (e.g., Mikhalevsky et al. 2015) and now it will be used in the central Arctic under in HiAOOS (see Section 2.1). The HiAOOS network in Fig.1 is building on the experiences and results from CAATEX. The technological goal has been to develop mooring networks that serves both traditional ice-ocean measurements, acoustic tomography, and geo-positioning of floats. In HiAOOS and HiAATS share the work-load and the costs, and involves several institutions with defined responsibilities.

Applications of the HiAOOS system in the Nansen and Amundsen Basin are described in section 4.1;4.3;4.4;4.5. The hope is that during the period the system is operational several groups will use the opportunity to put out additional moorings to listen to the signals or test positioning of floats.

Collaboration/Coordination: The three categories of mooring networks are complementary in their approach to improve the observing capacity of the ocean under the Arctic sea ice. It is therefore important to explore possible future collaboration and coordination between those networks. Projects, working with acoustic networks should aim to work together to facilitate dual use of sound sources and receivers to achieve both pan-Arctic coverage for acoustic tomography, under-ice geo-positioning, and communication.

Floats in the central Arctic.

Argo program is the largest world-wide system observing the interior of the ocean in near realtime, but the system is very limited in covering the Arctic Ocean. The new OneArgo design features algorithms for safe operation under sea ice, but it is still an issue to geo-position the profiles from the floats under the Arctic sea ice. To enhance high Arctic Argo coverage, an international Polar Argo mission team has been established aiming to enhance the Arctic Argo coverage. A new proposal Euro-Argo includes a task on the Argo design in the Arctic.

The acoustic network RIs should extend the collaboration with the Euro-Argo ERIC, as well as through the international Argo community to ensure that future floats to be used in the Arctic can take advantage of the new opportunities for under-ice geo-positioning. This can be followed up through links with the Polar Argo mission team, and directly with commercial providers of floats providers to ensure compatibility with the acoustic networks.

Buoys in the Arctic.

Drifting ice buoys placed on the ice and ice tethered profilers (ITP) are the only autonomous platforms that provide real time data from the central Arctic. The drifting ice buoys are relatively cheap, while the ITPs are relatively costly. Several buoys with different sensors and ITPs are often co-located and called ice observatories. See section 2.3 for more details. The data is sent via satellite and made available. With increasing communication bandwidth, we can expect the amount of data from the buoys and ITPs to increase.

Trans Arctic Cables.

Polar Connect is an initiative aiming for a fibre optic cable between Europe and Asia across the Arctic. This cable will provide data in real time and will thereby be a game changer for Arctic research and monitoring.

Collaboration between Polar Connect and groups utilizing sensors both on moored and autonomous platforms should be enhanced. A possibility to explore is if the groups can work towards together towards funding for both the cable installation and a sustained observing network. This is a huge effort, and it will be important to include communities in Europe as well as in North America and Asia. This is addressed by the UD-AOOS project.

Data management.

HiAOOS's efforts to develop and openly share standard methods for processing, analysis and visualization of ocean data are well received. This contributes to harmonization of data products from the high Arctic, along with similar but complementary efforts by e.g. the pan-Arctic DBO networks.

However, the new observing capabilities introduced by cables, pan Arctic mooring networks, floats, and buoys will introduce new challenges in building robust, secure and interoperable systems for data communication, storage, and distribution of data. The Ocean Network of Canada has developed a data management system for a distributed network of observing system, see Section 4.8. Collaboration with Ocean Network of Canada will be established as well as with other data management communities in Europe, US, Canada and Asia should be enhanced.

6 References

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Annex A: Program and participant list for workshop

Agenda

Wednesday 24 January 2024. 12:00 – 17:00

Lunch 12:00-13:00

Session 1: Overview of large projects with extensive field work in the central Arctic Ocean with emphasis on fixed observation infrastructures and measurement programs in the Central Arctic Ocean. Presentations should focus on the PURPOSE of the installations and how others could engage.

13:00-13:20 Welcome, introduction of participants, code of conduct (Arild & Hanne)

13:20-13:40 Hanne Sagen (NERSC) and M. Dzieciuch: HiAOOS and HiAATS projects.

13:40-14:00 Arild Sundfjord, Paul A. Dodd and Laura de Steur (NPI): NPI's Arctic Ocean mooring program.

14:00-14:20 Agnieszka Beszczynska (IOPAN): IOPAN moorings in HiAOOS and A-TWAIN

14:20-14:40 Benjamin Rabe (AWI) (remote): AWI's plans for Central Arctic Ocean research infrastructure deployments from 2024.

14:40-15:00. Craig Lee (UW), Lee Freitag (WHOI) et al: Ocean, Ice and Atmosphere in the Changing Arctic: Science & Technology Development in the Office of Naval Research Arctic Program

Coffee Break: 15:00-15:30

15:30-15:50 Anna Nikolopoulos (NPI) et al: Developing the pan-Arctic network of Distributed Biological Observatories (DBOs)

15:50-16:00 Eun-Jin Yang/Joo-Hong Kim (KOPRI) (presented by AS): KOPRI cruise and mooring plans in the Eastern Arctic 2024.

16:00-16:20 Igor Polyakov (IARC) (remote): The NABOS cruise and mooring program

16:20-17:15. Discussions: How to enhance collaboration and coordination? Define topics for further discussion.

1900. Dinner at Pastafabrikken (at your own expense)

24 January 2024

Thursday 25. January 2024

Session 2. Presentation of moving platforms programs including airborne platforms, sea ice buoys, floats, gliders, Argo buoys, etc. Presentations should focus on the PURPOSE of the measurements, data handling, and how others could engage. Discussions at the end of the session.

09:00-09:30. Craig Lee (UW), Lee Freitag (WHOI) et al: Technologies and Opportunities for Sustained, Autonomous Arctic Observing.

09:30-09:50. Virginie Ramasco (Akvaplan-niva) – A low-CO2 smart autonomous multiplatform system to monitor the Arctic Ocean.

09:50-10:05. Andreas Preußner (AWI) (remote): Sea ice buoys at AWI: Recent activities and plans for 2024/2025.

10:10-10:30. Coffee break

10:30-10:45. Claire Gourcuff (Euro-Argo) (remote): Euro-Argo in the Arctic.

10:45-11:00. Kjell Arne Mork (IMR) (remote): Nor-ARGO in the Arctic.

11:00-11:15. Agnieszka B. Møller (IOPAS): IOPAN floats in the Arctic under ArgoPoland.

11:15-11:30. Tom Rune Lauknes (NORCE): ARCTic Airborne Observing System (ARCAOS)

11:30-12:00. Discussion on Session 2, including links to fixed observation infrastructures.

Lunch Break 12:00-13:00

Session 3: Technologies, methods, tools and data delivery chains.

This session is focused on new developments to exploit the observing systems in different applications. A particular focus is on how new technologies, methods and tools can foster new applications as well as improve the delivery chains from multi sensor observing systems to data centers.

13:00-13:20. Matthew Dzieciuch (SIO): Acoustic technology for acoustic thermometry and geo-positioning

13:20-13:40. Lee Freitag (WHOI): Arctic Acoustics Communication and Navigation

13:40-14:00. Lora Van Uffelen (University of Rhode Island) – Acoustic propagation and underwater geo-positioning of moving platforms.

14:00-14:20. Espen Storheim: Localization of floats using the HiAOS multipurpose acoustic network.

14:20-14:40. Mathilde Sørensen (University of Bergen) – Earthquake monitoring in the Arctic combining seismological and passive acoustic data.

14:40-15:00. Agnieszka B. Møller (IOPAN) et al: Workflow for ocean and sea ice data in HiAOS.

Coffe Break: 15:00-15:20

15:20-15:40. Magnus Friberg (Vetenskapsrådet/SUNET): Polar Connect - Connectivity and sensors across the Arctic Ocean.

15:40-16:00. Benoît Pirenne (Ocean Networks Canada): Management of a multi-asset, integrated ocean observing system: data and infrastructure.

16:00-16:20. Torill Hamre (NERSC): Digital platforms and data delivery chains for marine in-situ observations.

16:20-16:40. Stein Tronstad (NPI): Data policies and licenses.

16:40-17:00. Discussion.

1900. Dinner at fabulous fish restaurant Arctandria (at your own expense).

24 January 2024

Friday 26. January 2024

09:00-12:00: Summary and discussion on Sessions 1,2 plus support assets

09:00-09:15: Arild Sundfjord (NPI): Overview of cruises in the Arctic Ocean 2024 and onward

09:15-09:30: Nick Hughes and Penelope Wagner - Ice information and satellite imaging to support vessel operations in the high Arctic.

09:30-10:30 Discussion

Suggestions for topics for discussions:

How can we make measurement programs efficient and coordinated? E.g. oceanographic sections, bathymetric data, sea ice stations, buoy distribution, sensor configuration in moorings.

Can we share operational support: e.g. sea ice and weather services. Can acquisition, processing and distribution of remote sensing products be optimized and shared? How to best use, share and store sea ice and weather forecasting products. Can the different cruises and infrastructures provide calibration/Fiducial Reference Measurements for remote sensing? Environmental assessments for field work?

10:30-11:00. Coffee Break

11:00-11:45. Discussion about new technologies, methods, tools, and data.

Summary of the application areas addressed in the workshop with emphasis on how new technologies can engage new user groups.

Examples of topics for discussion:

How can technologies, methods, and tools be shared?

How can we benefit from new technology: communication, cables, autonomous platforms and drone technology, AI, digital platforms.

Are there any legislative issues?

11:45-12:00 Summary of the workshop and next steps for continued collaboration.

1200-1300 Lunch

[Participant list on next page]

24 January 2024

Participants

First name	Surname	Institution
Arild	Sundfjord	Norwegian Polar Institute
Hanne	Sagen	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
Craig	Lee	University of Washington – Applied Physics Laboratory
Matthew	Dzieciuch	Scripps Institution of Oceanography
Lee	Freitag	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Nick	Hughes	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
Agnieszka	Beszczynska-Möller	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Science
Benoît	Pirenne	Ocean Networks Canada
*Igor	Polyakov	International Arctic Research Centre, Fairbanks, Alaska
*Benjamin	Rabe	Alfred Wegener Institute
Magnus	Friberg	Sunet
*Claire	Gourcuff	Euro-Argo
Anna	Nikolopoulos	Norwegian Polar Institute
Connie Elise	Solberg	Norwegian Defence Research Establishment
Stein	Sandven	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
Rolf	Rødven	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program AMAP
Mathilde	Sørensen	University of Bergen
Penelope	Wagner	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
Dag	Tollefsen	Norwegian Defence Research Establishment
Lora	Van Uffelen	University of Rhode Island
Tom Rune	Lauknes	NORCE
Laura	de Steur	Norwegian Polar Institute
Roald	Otnes	Norwegian Defence Research Establishment
Virginie	Ramasco	Akvaplan-niva
La	Hyoung Sul	Korean Polar Research Institute
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Espen	Storheim	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
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Torill	Hamre	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

* = online

24 January 2024

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